

Review Article

Pioneers without support? A systematic literature review about outdoor education in secondary schools

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ABSTRACT

This article systematically reviews the literature on outdoor education in secondary schools (grades 7 to 9). The systematic literature review illustrates the findings available on continuous, curriculum-based, subject-related outdoor education at the secondary level. Based on the PRISMA statement, five literature databases were searched for articles published between 2020 and 2024. This resulted in 150 different articles, six of which met predefined inclusion criteria. These were analyzed both from the perspective of outdoor education and from a school improvement perspective. The results show that outdoor education is practiced differently and is subject to numerous challenges. There is a need for additional research, further practical examples and corresponding school improvement processes.

1. Introduction

Pierce and Beames (2024) ask, in the context of outdoor education, where the “E” has gone in the “OE” of Irish outdoor education. This question is relevant beyond the Irish context: What is actually taught and learned in outdoor education? What is the educational value of outdoor education? In an era where test-based accountability and thus the performance orientation of schools are becoming increasingly dominant in schools (James & Williams, 2017; Torres, 2021), this question has become essential. The literature reveals numerous benefits of outdoor education (see, for example, the list of corresponding Canadian studies in Asfeldt et al., 2022; the literature review by Becker et al., 2017; or the international comparison by Waite, 2022). In most cases, these are interdisciplinary skills or positive influences of outdoor education on well-being and health. A typology of research on “learning outside the classroom” (LOtC) shows that 78 % of the research (included in the corresponding review) exclusively mentions soft skills as the goal of outdoor education (Hawxwell et al., 2019). Curriculum-based subject-related learning was the goal of outdoor education in only 20 % of the articles (Hawxwell et al., 2019). The reviews by Becker et al. (2017) and Kuo et al. (2022) show that there are various studies that confirm that outdoor education has a direct positive effect on students’ learning. Concretely, the students’ academic performance (e.g. reading and writing competences) improves when nature is integrated into teaching compared to traditional classroom teaching. They even speak of a “dose-response relationship” (Kuo et al., 2022, p. 50), according to

which the learning gain is proportional to the dose of nature (Kuo et al., 2022; with reference to Wells et al., 2015). The authors stress: “Findings have been consistently positive across diverse student populations, academic subjects, instructors and instructional approaches, educational settings, and research designs” (Kuo et al., 2022, p. 55). Mann et al. (2022) report that control groups sometimes achieved the same results as classes that utilized outdoor education, but that there are additional benefits associated with outdoor education: “This suggests whilst curricular lessons in the local outdoors may not inhibit or accelerate academic performance, they can particularly impact students’ wellbeing and engagement” (Mann et al., 2022, p. 8). Based on this source, outdoor education yields no greater learning gains than classroom learning, but it has other advantages. Thus, it can be concluded that, while achieving learning goals is not an argument against outdoor learning compared to classroom learning, there are numerous other advantages that speak in favour of outdoor education.

Articles reviewed use different concepts of outdoor education as well as varied definitions. In this article, a broad understanding of outdoor education is pursued, similar to the LOtC understanding, which is based on learning outside the classroom (Department for Education and Skills, 2006; Hawxwell et al., 2019), whereby a restriction is made to outdoor locations such as nature, cultural spaces or the school environment (based on Kühnis et al., 2024). Learning can take place through nature or the respective location as well as simply in this location using created teaching materials. The possibility of teaching outdoors without explicitly including the environment is also left open in the taxonomy of

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Mannion et al. (2011) and Kelly et al. (2022): If the lesson takes place outdoors but could just as easily be taught in a classroom, the term “place-ambivalent” is used. However, if the environment is important or even essential for the lesson, outdoor education is referred to as “place-sensitive” or even “place-essential” because it is learning “with the outdoors providing the context, resources, setting and/or space for rich experiential and authentic learning” (Kelly et al., 2022, p. 76). In the understanding of the term in this article, the focus of outdoor education is not primarily on environmental education, but on subject-related, curriculum-oriented learning that takes place outdoors. This understanding of the term essentially corresponds to the outdoor education model by Kühnis et al. (2024). According to this idea, outdoor education is understood as curriculum-based, continuous, experience-oriented and discovery-based learning in cultural spaces, on school grounds and in the natural environment, where engagement with the real-life environment is possible and learning opportunities exist for all subjects. The Danish Udeskole has a similar understanding of outdoor education (Barfod et al., 2021). Outdoor education with an environmental focus is, for example, discovering the flow speed of a river directly outside instead of understanding or reconstructing it based on books or using representations in the classroom.

Literature on outdoor education often refers to kindergarten and primary level, where outdoor education is more likely to take place than at the secondary level (Barfod et al., 2021; Scott et al., 2015; Williams & Scott, 2019; Winje & Løndal, 2021). Consequently there is little literature or research on outdoor education at the secondary level – as this literature review will show in detail. This research gap is addressed in this paper with the aim of providing a basis for advancing research on secondary level outdoor education. This article relates the findings available on continuous, curriculum-based, subject-related outdoor teaching and learning at the secondary level (school years 7–9). It also identifies where there may be a need for support from secondary schools to promote outdoor education and where future studies on outdoor education at the secondary level can start. In addition, the trend in educational reforms will be considered, where test-based accountability and the resulting focus on academic achievement are important factors (James & Williams, 2017; Torres, 2021). This results in a narrowing of the curriculum, which also has an impact on outdoor education. For example, there is barely any room for in-context learning (Berliner, 2011; Blazer, 2011; James & Williams, 2017) because “teachers now and then feel uncertain whether the teaching and learning [outdoors] is truly educational enough in terms of the acquisition of testable skills” (Barfod und Mygind, 2022, p. 291). So, teachers adapt the lesson content, their teaching style and the test format due to high-stakes testing (see summary in Blazer, 2011 based on a broad literature database). To this end, a systematic literature review (based on the PRISMA statement, see Page et al., 2021; Petticrew & Roberts, 2006) will be carried out to determine the state of research on secondary school level outdoor education over the last five years.

2. Existing literature reviews

At first glance, in the field of outdoor education, there are numerous literature reviews (since 2020, including the following Birdwell et al., 2024; Falzon & Conrad, 2024; Gruno & Gibbons, 2022; Janes et al., 2024; Kilty & Burrows, 2020; Kuo et al., 2022; Mann et al., 2021, 2022; Mansfield et al., 2020; Remmen & Iversen, 2023; Richardson et al., 2024; Sulfa et al., 2024; Wolf et al., 2022). Some of the literature reviews are broad in scope, while others have a narrower focus. However, only a few refer to the secondary level or at least include this level. Two reviews in which the secondary level was included are discussed below.

In their literature review, Becker et al. (2017) examined the outcomes of regular formal, school-based and curriculum-based outdoor education for five to 18-year-old students. They divided the outcomes into three categories: outcomes in the area of learning, in the area of social dimensions, and other outcomes (in particular physical health,

but also environmentally-friendly behavior). On the one hand, their literature review showed that until 2016 there were only a few studies dealing with formal, regular outdoor education. On the other hand, they also came to the conclusion that their literature review revealed trends “which indicate that regular compulsory school- and curriculum-based outdoor education programs can advance students in the physical, psychological, learning and social dimensions” (Becker et al., 2017, p. 17). In another broad international literature review, the socio-emotional and academic benefits of nature-based outdoor education were presented in almost 150 studies (60 % of them secondary schools; school years 7–12) from 2000 to 2020 (Mann et al., 2022). Outdoor education was defined broadly: it took place not only in the “traditional school subjects [were] taught in natural environments” (Mann et al., 2022, p. 1), but also as adventure education, in the school garden or on excursions. The literature review showed that outdoor education has multiple benefits. For secondary school students, outdoor education led to an increase in self-competence and social skills in 40 and 30 of the 88 studies examined respectively. Outdoor education was also beneficial for mental and emotional health, well-being, environmental knowledge and the attitude of secondary school students towards the environment, as well as motivation to learn, as shown in nearly a dozen of the studies. Academic learning gains were only mentioned as an outcome of outdoor education in eight of the 88 secondary school studies considered (Mann et al., 2022, p. 6).

Both literature reviews demonstrate that subject-related, academic learning is to a certain extent linked to outdoor education, but that there are scarcely any studies on *continuous* outdoor education (Becker et al., 2017), or that academic learning seems to be of less importance than the promotion of soft skills (Mann et al., 2022). This is where the present literature review comes in: It looks at studies from 2020 onwards and focuses on regular, curriculum-based, subject-related outdoor education at the secondary level (school years 7–9).

3. Research questions

A – still unsystematic – look at the literature shows that secondary school students do come into contact with the “outdoors” during school, for example as part of the school subject outdoor adventure, as is the case in North America (see, for example, Shirilla et al., 2022) or as part of excursions (see, for example, Celik & Aydın, 2024; Chik et al., 2024), project weeks and camps (see, for example, Evans & Acton, 2022; Jane et al., 2022). However, this seems to be more about experiencing nature and learning how to deal with or survive in nature as well as learning soft skills, or “life skills”, using the term used by the World Health Organization (1994), than about relocalizing traditional lessons. Only a few articles deal with students who learn traditional school subjects such as language, mathematics, science or art outdoors or teachers who teach these subjects outdoors (see, for example, Ndzimbomvu et al., 2021). Texts in which the corresponding school improvement processes – for example “the path to regular outdoor education” – are described also seem to be rare. From this subjective perception based on the examination of publications on outdoor education, the need for a systematic literature review emerges, in which the state of research on secondary level outdoor education is *systematically* researched and analyzed.

This article addresses this need: By means of a systematic literature review, an overview of literature on outdoor education at the secondary school level (school years 7–9; students aged 12 to 15) is compiled. For this purpose, articles published from 2020 to 2024 that address continuous, curriculum-oriented, subject-related outdoor education (in contrast to, for example, primarily interdisciplinary learning) are considered. The focus is reminiscent of Becker et al. (2017), who speak of “regular compulsory school- and curriculum-based OEP [outdoor education programs]”. The articles are analyzed both from the *perspective of outdoor education* and from a *school improvement perspective*, as outdoor education not only changes the place of teaching, but also alters the school organization and way of teaching (Sahrakhiz, 2018). The

school order, which is geared towards classroom teaching, is shaken by outdoor education (Feichter, 2020; Tyack & Tobin, 1994). Outdoor education is not something that the teacher(s) can pursue individually, but is dependent on support from the teaching staff and school management (Müller-Kuhn et al., 2024).

The literature review is based on the following questions.

- How does continuous, curriculum-oriented, subject-related outdoor education take place at the secondary level, what are the goals of outdoor education and what challenges are mentioned?
- How is continuous outdoor education launched, developed and supported in secondary schools?
- How is outdoor education embedded in the literature?

4. Method

The systematic literature review is based on the PRISMA 2020 statement (Page et al., 2021) and the suggestions for systematic literature reviews by Petticrew and Roberts (2006). It was organized using the following steps.

Step 1 – Research in five databases – identification of records

The databases ERIC (via ProQuest), Green File (via EBSCO), Web of Science, PsycInfoAPA (via OVID) and FIS-Bildung (for texts in German) were searched for articles on secondary level outdoor education published in German or English from 2020 to 2024. The terms *nature based learning (nbl)*, *environmental education*, *environmental learning*, *nature school*, *natural learning*, *outdoor education*, *education outdoor*, *outdoor education programmes*, *outdoor learning*, *learning outdoor*, *outdoor teaching*, *teaching outdoor*, *education outside the classroom (EOTC)*, *out-of-classroom*, *learning outside the classroom*, *traditional school subjects taught in natural environments*, *expeditionary learning*, *adventure education*, *adventure learning*, *place-based education*, *place-based learning*, *udeskole*, *uteskole*, *utomhuspedagogik*, *friluftsliv*, *forest school* as well as in German *Draussenlernen*, *Draussenunterricht*, *Draussenschule*, *Lernen im Freien* were used to search for articles. The terms *secondary school*, *secondary education*, *lower secondary education*, *mandatory secondary education*, *middle school*, *junior high school*, *junior secondary* and in German *Sekundarschule*, *Sekundarstufe*, *Zyklus 3* were selected for the search by level.¹ The terms were taken from various texts, including the research conducted by Becker et al. (2017), Hawxwell et al. (2019) and Mann et al. (2022), but also from other sources (e.g. the anthology by Jucker & Von Au, 2022). The keyword search referred to the title and abstract in each case. Filtering was also carried out for the document type “Article”, the publication type “Academic Journal” and for peer reviewed. The results list was saved in the reference management program Zotero.

Step 2 – Removing duplicate articles

The results from each of the five database searches were compared so that articles resulting from more than one search could be marked. An Excel list was created in which all articles were listed and it was noted from which database or databases each article originated.

Step 3 – Assessment based on title and abstract

The defined inclusion criteria were applied to the title and abstract, in which the title and abstract were manually read in full. The inclusion criteria were both formal and content-related. The following formal

inclusion criteria were applied²: year of publication (2020–2024), language (English or German), text type (empirical study, journal article; exclusion criteria: obituaries or literature reviews) and target group (cycle 3/secondary level 1, school years 7–9, students aged 12 to 16; minimum requirement: at least one grade addressed in the article had to overlap with one of the target school years). The inclusion criteria in terms of content were as follows: The article had to examine curriculum-based school lessons that regularly took place outdoors and included subject-related learning (following the regular compulsory school- and curriculum-based outdoor education programs; Becker et al., 2017). Exclusion criteria were: no reference to outdoor education; individual outdoor education lessons; pure effectiveness evaluation of a teaching unit (in the sense of “Do the students know more about a specific topic after the lesson compared to before the lesson?”). A decision was made for each article as to whether it met the formal and content criteria and was therefore included in the next round, or whether it was excluded. In order to have an overview of the excluded articles, the general premise of each one was noted.

Step 4 – Assessment based on full text

The full texts of the articles selected in the third step were read. The defined inclusion and exclusion criteria used in the third step were again applied. Based on the full texts, it was decided whether the articles would be excluded or used for the final evaluation.

Step 5 – Detailed analysis in Maxqda

The final texts were analyzed in Maxqda. Text passages relevant to the research questions were coded in terms of content. The code tree was created along the lines of the questions and further subcategories were added inductively. The structure of the code tree comprises the following main categories.

- Implementation (design, objectives and challenges)
- Introduction and support (school improvement perspective)
- Localization/discourse
- Context information such as country

Summary grids were created for the main categories, which formed the basis for the results presented in the following chapter.

5. Results

Table 1 provides an overview of the numerical results of the five steps of analysis. The literature search yielded 150 articles (after the reduction of articles that appeared more than once; see Appendix B). Of these 150, six articles dealt with continuous, curriculum-oriented, subject-related outdoor education and 144 articles did not meet the formal and/or content-related criteria which were excluded from the main part of the systematic literature review. The articles excluded for content reasons nevertheless provide indications of the state of research on outdoor education at the secondary level, which is why these articles are taken up in the following subchapter before the main results of the literature review are presented.

5.1. Irregular, non-curriculum-based, non-subject-related outdoor education at secondary level (insight into the excluded articles)

Failure to meet the content criteria of the systematic literature review excluded 115 articles in steps 3 and 4. For the most part, these

¹ The complete search string can be found in Appendix A.

² As much as possible, these were already set in the first step using the filter function of the search. Nevertheless, they were checked again manually in the third step.

Table 1
Overview of the exclusion or selection of articles.

	Number of articles
Step 1 – Research in five databases; identification of records	
Green File via EBSCO	25
ERIC via ProQuest	73
Psychinfo via Ovid	23
Web of Science	116
FisBildung (German)	0
<i>Total number of articles</i>	<i>237</i>
Step 2 – Removing duplicate articles	
Number of articles after removing duplicates	150
Step 3 – Assessment based on title and abstract	
Reports assessed for eligibility	13
Excluded due to formal criteria (language, level, etc.)	28
Excluded due to content	109
Step 4 – Assessment based on full text	
Reports assessed for eligibility (selected for detailed analysis)	6
Excluded due to formal criteria (language, level, etc.)	1
Excluded due to content	6
Step 5 – Detailed analysis in Maxqda	
Coded articles for content analysis (total studies included in review)	6

articles did not address continuous outdoor education, but rather a one-time outdoor education event, the evaluation of a prepared teaching unit or the topic of environmental education, which was not always pursued outdoors but in the classroom. If the title and/or abstract did not suggest that the article discussed continuous, curriculum-oriented outdoor education in which subject-specific learning had at least some relevance, it was excluded in step 3. If the title and/or abstract indicated that continuous, curriculum-oriented outdoor education could be the focus of the article and that subject-specific learning might have at least some relevance, the article was taken to step 4, where a decision was made based on the full-text reading as to whether it fit the content-related questions of the systematic literature review or was excluded after all.

For each article that was excluded in the third or fourth step for content reasons, the main topic of the article was recorded. The evaluation of this coding shows that 78 of the 115 articles excluded for content-related reasons were about environmental education. Environmental education referred to various sub-topics such as climate change (Karim et al., 2022), marine environment (Alves et al., 2024), energy efficiency (Drosos et al., 2021), or waste separation (Zhang et al., 2024), or testing instruments for assessing environmental skills (Mujib et al., 2023). Furthermore, there were five texts each focusing on ESD (education for sustainable development) and place-based education. The former dealt with, for example, a survey of students' knowledge of ESD (Agirreazkuenaga & Martinez, 2021) and the contribution of physical education teachers to ESD (Froberg et al., 2023). The articles on place-based education included place-based reading as a method for outdoor education (Eggersen, 2024) and Indigenous place-based stories (Kinch et al., 2022). Several articles centered on health and well-being, for example solutions for students who sit for too long (Parrish et al., 2023) or the use of a nature journal to help combat poor mental health in students (Arbor & Matteson, 2023). The literature body also included articles on topics such as religiosity (Altmeyer & Dreesmann, 2020), geoethics (Georgousis et al., 2021), curriculum (Norman & Wall, 2020) and digitalization (Leitao et al., 2022). The articles that were excluded but nevertheless emerged from the systematic literature search thus indicate the following: Environmental education is of great importance in secondary education. The research situation is relatively broad and global: environmental education is practiced and researched in countries on all continents. However, environmental education is not always taught outdoors. Numerous articles showed that environmental

education takes place in the classroom. Other articles focused on students who consciously use the environment in which they are located. The keyword here is place-based education. Several articles described one-time outdoor teaching units. The fact that lessons at the secondary level take place outdoors on a regular basis, with reference to the curriculum and as subject lessons (i.e. not primarily to strengthen interdisciplinary skills, but for subject learning) was not the focus of these 115 articles. It seems that there has been very little research conducted on this topic to date.

5.2. Overview of articles on outdoor education at the secondary school level

Of the 150 total articles – as can be seen from steps 4 and 5 – six articles addressed continuous outdoor education with a curriculum and subject reference. Table 2 provides a brief overview of the selected articles. The content analysis of the selected articles offers insights into the state of research on continuous, curriculum-oriented, subject-related outdoor education at or including the secondary level. The results of the analysis are presented in the following sub-chapters in line with the questions formulated at the beginning.

5.3. Implementation of outdoor education at the secondary level (research question 1)

Across the six articles analyzed, outdoor education is implemented in very different ways. This subchapter provides insight into outdoor learning practice at the secondary level, divided into practice, goals and challenges.

5.3.1. Practice of outdoor education

Primary experiences played a central role in outdoor education (Duggan et al., 2021; Höper, 2024). One student described it as follows: “you can touch something and see it in your hand then it makes a lot of sense to me. With books, it's sometimes harder” (Duggan et al., 2021, p. 125). Outdoor education was often designed in such a way that a connection to the environment, and in some cases also to learning in the classroom, was established: Salmon were bred in the classroom, for which the most suitable place to release them was then sought; Water quality was examined and the presence of invasive species was taken

Table 2
Overview of articles included in the analysis.

Article	Contents	Country	Method	School levels
Duggan et al. (2021)	Interdisciplinary lessons that relate closely to the local environment, in particular the impact of climate change on the coastal region: Outdoor subject teaching (mathematics, English and natural sciences) with the long-term goal of achieving environmental education for the general population. Factors contributing to the success of outdoor lessons are one of the results of the project.	South Africa (Author from South Africa and USA)	Participatory observation, interviews, group discussion, feedback sessions	Kindergarten to grade 9; grades 7–9 with mixed-age classes
Gruno and Gibbons (2021)	Introduction of nature-based physical education: Project which aims to support girls' physical education engagement through nature-based physical activities (NBPA). The study revealed the characteristics of NBPA, differences from previous outdoor education efforts in physical education and challenges in implementing NBPA.	Canada	Focus group interviews with teaching staff from 13 schools	School years 6–12
Hamilton and Marckini-Polk (2023)	Investigation of outdoor education in two classes, including influencing factors and students' learning gain, supported by a watershed education experiences program: Interdisciplinary teaching where one class raised salmon and looked for the ideal place to release the fish, the other class explored biodiversity in the watershed. Findings led to generalizable implications for outdoor education.	USA	Self-assessments, group interviews with the two teachers and their 200 students	School years 7–8
Höper (2024)	Conducting chemistry lessons outside the classroom: Investigation of how pre-service teachers' beliefs influence outdoor chemistry teaching, showing that meaningful links between phenomena and chemistry foster teaching chemistry outdoors.	Norway	Drawing assignment, mind maps, interviews with six teachers	School years 1–11
Kervinen et al. (2020)	Regular outdoor teaching by three biology teachers in contrast to teachers who only teach indoors: Exploration of how the teachers managed to include outdoor education in the formal curriculum, leading to three key elements of a successful implementation process: regularity, justification and promoting the students' freedom.	Finland	Interviews with three teachers	Secondary school with students aged 13–15 years
Svobodová et al. (2021)	Overview study on the status of outdoor education in the Czech Republic: Examining how outdoor education is implemented in schools in terms of location, time, topics and learning progress; four principles of outdoor education were then developed from the analysis.	Czech Republic	Content analysis of 50 school programs and interviews with teachers from nine schools	Secondary level was represented by lower secondary level and lower classes of the grammar school

into account ([Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023](#)). Forest and water ecosystems were addressed in biology ([Kervinen et al., 2020](#)), physical education was taught with nature in mind ([Gruno & Gibbons, 2021](#)) and lessons were created to make connections to environmental issues in various subjects such as math, science, English and art ([Duggan et al., 2021](#)). Connections were made to the school environment, to the students' living environment and the learning was designed to have a benefit for the place or community ([Duggan et al., 2021](#); [Svobodová et al., 2021](#)). Lessons were primarily interdisciplinary and a connection to classroom learning was seen as essential ([Duggan et al., 2021](#); [Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023](#); [Svobodová et al., 2021](#)). Some students were continuously assessed, for example for search tasks in nature and correctly naming what they found ([Kervinen et al., 2020](#)). Teachers sometimes chose topics based on their own preferences, but also by the usefulness of what was learned to the students' lives ([Svobodová et al., 2021](#)). They prepared lessons in a similar way to classroom lessons or even more meticulously ([Svobodová et al., 2021](#)). Outdoor education occurred in different places – depending on which location was suitable for the respective lesson content ([Svobodová et al., 2021](#)). Outdoor education should happen regularly or at least frequently so that a routine develops and outdoor education is seen as a teaching lesson and not just a fun outing ([Kervinen et al., 2020](#)). Outdoor education can last one lesson, a whole day or several days, with the latter then no longer being carried out regularly but occasionally ([Svobodová et al., 2021](#)).

Thus, very different forms of outdoor education emerge from the

literature review. Many teaching units were related to environmental education and referred to the places found (keyword place-based education; see [Sobel, 2004](#); [Yemini et al., 2025](#)). Outdoor education units have different frequencies. Consistent implementation improves the perception that outdoor education is actual school instruction. As quoted from one article: “The teachers needed to use ways to make outdoor lessons resemble ordinary school activity. Regularity, assessment and a supportive curriculum as well as cooperation within a school were used to justify outdoor teaching to the students as ‘real school-work’” ([Kervinen et al., 2020](#), p. 124).

5.3.2. Goals of outdoor education

The goals pursued with outdoor education are diverse. At times outdoor education is used as a means to an end: for example, it serves to enable individual projects by students, to realize interdisciplinary teacher cooperation, employed as teaching development projects, or is used to increase the motivation of female students in sports ([Gruno & Gibbons, 2021](#); [Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023](#); [Svobodová et al., 2021](#)). In some cases, a connected goal is also environmental and community benefits ([Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023](#)) or environmental education, which in turn focuses on the immediate natural environment, such as bodies of water ([Duggan et al., 2021](#); [Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023](#)). With outdoor education, schools also want to expose students to the world outside of school, so that they understand larger contexts in nature, may become competent adults, and share

knowledge with those less educated in the local population (Duggan et al., 2021). Outdoor education also explicitly concerns technical, academic learning (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023; Höper, 2024).

These objectives illustrate that subject-related learning is not always the main goal of outdoor education. Outdoor education prioritizes goals other than purely classical, subject-related ones as well. So subject-related learning can be both the goal of outdoor education and the means to achieve another positive outcome.

5.3.3. Challenges in connection with outdoor education

In addition to the descriptions of outdoor education implementation, the articles also revealed challenges with which teachers in particular are confronted. It is striking that only rarely were challenges mentioned that related to the implementation of the actual outdoor lessons themselves. One such challenge was mentioned in connection with chemistry lessons: For the school subject of chemistry, teachers found it difficult to react to what they might find outside and integrate this spontaneously into chemistry lessons or even into an experiment (Höper, 2024). Some teachers reported that they had too few skills to teach outdoors or that they did not have enough confidence, including in terms of risk management (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021). One challenge that lies at the interface between on-site implementation and planning is the accessibility of the location where outdoor education takes place, especially when the class includes students who have special needs (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021). The majority of challenges mentioned related to organizational and administrative matters as well as preparatory work: For example, teachers had to obtain parental consent, an accompanying person was needed and missed lessons in other subjects had to be made up (Svobodová et al., 2021). In addition, there may be a lack of resources and teaching materials for outdoor education, such as in underprivileged schools in South Africa (Duggan et al., 2021), or obtaining funding for outdoor sports equipment may be a challenge (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021). A lack of parental acceptance of outdoor education (especially if outdoor education conflicts with a family's religious background), or objections from students or the Ministry of Education, can pose additional challenges (Duggan et al., 2021; Gruno & Gibbons, 2021). In a case of lack of trust from the Ministry of Education, one school no longer dared to teach outdoors because it did not want to deviate from the intended curriculum due to strict Ministry of Education control. (Duggan et al., 2021). In another case, the need for legitimization materialized with school management: outdoor education was not considered teaching or working time for the teacher, so all the time spent on field trips or other outdoor education the teacher was required to make up as working time inside the school building (Svobodová et al., 2021). Another frequently-mentioned challenge is the limited time available for outdoor education: After a lesson outside, a different teacher usually teaches the next subject (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021; Svobodová et al., 2021). The requirement to teach outdoor education as interdisciplinary is also a challenge, especially if the respective subjects are taught by different teachers (Duggan et al., 2021). This challenge was solved in concrete terms through team teaching (Duggan et al., 2021).

Of the challenges listed to lessons being held outdoors at the secondary school level – only a few challenges relating to teaching itself were mentioned. With appropriate training and further education for teachers, it should be possible to significantly reduce these barriers. The hurdle seems to lie more in the organization of outdoor education.

5.4. Launching, development and support of outdoor education at the secondary level (research question 2)

The systematic literature review reveals both experiences and desiderata regarding the launching, development and support of outdoor education. This provides a view of the topic from the perspective of school improvement. The launching, development and support of outdoor education at the secondary level is divided into five sub-codes,

which also form the structure of this sub-chapter.

5.4.1. Reliability

The articles analyzed show that certain reliability is necessary for continuous, curriculum-oriented and subject-related outdoor education, which teachers in particular would like to see: For example, it is helpful if outdoor education is anchored in the curriculum – so that teachers can orient themselves towards it (Svobodová et al., 2021), but also so that they have a clear basis for legitimizing and justifying outdoor education (Kervinen et al., 2020). A school-specific, school-wide outdoor education concept also seems to be rare but helpful; teachers would like this for all outdoor education units that are not one-off events (Svobodová et al., 2021). Depending on the subject that is taught and learned outdoors, the need for support fluctuates (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021). The support that teachers perceive from their school management has a positive effect on their self-image with respect to outdoor education (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). It is supportive when annual goals are set (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023); however, it seems to be difficult for teachers if there is a lack of commitment and continuity, for example, if they are assigned a new class after the first year of outdoor education and cannot build on experiences from the previous year (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023).

In summary, it is clear from the studies to date that teachers need commitment in the sense of clear orientation points, ideally through the curriculum, and that continuity, predictability, and reliability help them to not only carry out outdoor education, but also to develop it further, for which a supportive school management and ideally national decision-makers are necessary.

5.4.2. External references and relationships

When introducing and implementing outdoor education, schools may employ external specialists such as nature educators (Duggan et al., 2021; Svobodová et al., 2021) or researchers (Duggan et al., 2021). In one case, the constant supplementing research contributed to the school's continuation of outdoor education (Duggan et al., 2021). Showing or using connections to the school environment and the community at large helped to ensure that outdoor education seemed meaningful to students (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). Through appropriate homework, outdoor education also indirectly educated parents (Duggan et al., 2021). One article pointed out the relevance of links between outdoor education and the local environment as follows: "most impactful PBE [place-based education] learning experiences will be those that empower teachers to integrate voice and choice for students, ensure that students' learning and work connects to their local communities, and make clear the ways students' work directly and positively impact their local environments" (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023, p. 18).

From the analysis of the articles, it can be summarized that external references and relationships are of great importance for outdoor education for various reasons including support, maintenance, motivation, and reach.

5.4.3. Attitude

The introduction and support of outdoor education not only takes place on a directly visible level, but the article analysis also showed that what teachers think about outdoor education, how they communicate and what attitude they embody are also relevant: If teachers are convinced of the advantages of outdoor education – or of place-based education – they feel empowered to do outdoor education even if no other teacher in the school building does outdoor education (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). If a teacher embodies the attitude that outdoor education is a regular lesson and not just a visit to the forest, the students also adopted this attitude and defended their outdoor education even against critical voices from other students in the school who were not having outdoor education (Kervinen et al., 2020). One teacher described the students as follows: "The students get a feeling that it's not just an

add-on, that now we're just going to have some fun outdoors. But instead it's real studying" (Kervinen et al., 2020, p. 120). Regularity, outdoor assessments, a supportive curriculum, and cooperation within the school are conducive to internalizing such an attitude (Kervinen et al., 2020).

5.4.4. Exchange – in terms of content and organization

Two findings emerge from the literature review regarding the exchange between teachers regarding outdoor education: Firstly, there were barely any exchange meetings within a school team, for example because only one teacher in the school building carried out outdoor education. This was criticized by the teachers and led to them feel isolated and left alone (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). These teachers then found opportunities for exchange outside of their school: as part of a program that supported them with resources for outdoor education, there were meetings for an exchange of content among the teachers (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). In the nationwide study in the Czech Republic, exchange was also difficult, but not because there were no other outdoor education teachers at the school, but rather they did not really cooperate with each other: it was difficult to reach agreement among the teachers, for example to make adjustments to the timetable so that a teacher could spend more than the duration of a single lesson outside (Svobodová et al., 2021). When teachers decided to teach outdoors together, the lessons were not very interdisciplinary, but rather a sequential series of subject lessons (Svobodová et al., 2021).

The results therefore show that teachers want to exchange ideas with other teachers who teach outdoors and are therefore dependent on having contact with teachers who also teach outdoors – ideally in their own school. At the same time however, the presence of several teachers teaching outdoors does not mean that exchanges are automatically beneficial, let alone sufficient. Hamilton and Marckini-Polk (2023, p. 18) summarize: "One thing this study makes clear is that robust PBE [place-based education] is particularly challenging in the absence of additional on-site colleagues and intentional, interdisciplinary teaching and learning opportunities."

5.4.5. Teacher-centeredness

Teachers are the linchpin of beneficial outdoor education (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). To ensure that they have sufficient confidence to teach outdoors, it helps if subject-related outdoor teaching is already part of the teachers' training and they are gradually introduced to subject-related outdoor teaching (Höper, 2024). It was found that more experienced teachers were less willing to try new things than younger teachers (Duggan et al., 2021). Moving lessons outside requires courage from teachers because the process is often open (Svobodová et al., 2021).

The literature review shows that teachers, or rather their willingness and confidence, are of central importance for successful outdoor education, which can be positively influenced by appropriate training.

5.5. Embedding outdoor education in the literature (research question 3)

In the articles analyzed, outdoor education is embedded in larger contexts and discourses, but also in specific findings: Several articles started from the realization that many positive effects emanate from outdoor education (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021; Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023; Höper, 2024; Svobodová et al., 2021). Furthermore, outdoor education was embedded in curriculum reform and a country's communist past (Svobodová et al., 2021) or in concrete findings such as the low engagement of girls in physical education (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021). Embedding outdoor education in larger discourses took place in the field of environmental education, place-based education and with regard to various models and theoretical concepts, as elaborated in the following sub-chapters.

5.5.1. Environmental education

Outdoor education has been placed in the context of environmental education on several occasions. Doing so involves both knowledge and environmental skills (Duggan et al., 2021; Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). It also includes a connection with nature (Gruno & Gibbons, 2021) and concrete experiences in or with nature (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023). This suggests that outdoor education does not happen in isolation from the environment, but that the environment is an essential aspect of outdoor education.

5.5.2. Place-based education and experiential education

Several articles (Duggan et al., 2021; Gruno & Gibbons, 2021; Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023) focused their research on outdoor education in the field of place-based education, such as the study from South Africa, which described that they teach knowledge about climate change and changing ocean conditions and that their own region, especially the seashores, were of central importance for outdoor education in these schools (Duggan et al., 2021).

The concept of experiential education is a sub-aspect of place-based education (Sobel, 2004; Yemini et al., 2025), in which teaching refers to the local community and the environment or the school's surroundings. With reference to Dewey (1938), it essentially implies that people learn through experience. This concept is also referenced to embed outdoor education in it (Hamilton & Marckini-Polk, 2023).

In one article in this literature review (Höper, 2024) however, the cultural, social and political aspects of place-based education, seemed to be too narrow, with that author preferring to use the more neutral term "outdoor education", with reference to the Scandinavian concept of Udeskole (Barfod et al., 2021).

This shows that outdoor education at the secondary level has repeatedly been embedded in the discourse of place-based education and that place-based education is an important frame of reference for – not all, but many – studies on outdoor education.

5.5.3. Further models and theoretical concepts

Outdoor education is also embedded in other models or theoretical concepts. As the models and theoretical concepts listed below were referenced in just one article, only a rough outline of them is provided here.

One such model is interdisciplinary learning in the natural sciences, which can also be found in the Norwegian curriculum. It combines the individual scientific disciplines so that there are science lessons, rather than chemistry, biology and physics as separate subjects (Höper, 2024).

Another model combines several concepts at once (Hilburn & Maguth, 2011): It combines interdisciplinary teaching and place-based education and adds another component of what is called successful learning: Thus, learning should not only be interdisciplinary and place-based, but also intentional. This is also a concept that was used as a basis for an article on outdoor education (Duggan et al., 2021).

Another concept in which outdoor education (Kervinen et al., 2020) has been embedded is the concept of processes and mechanisms of institutionalization (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Specifically, the authors were guided by the fact that institutionalization begins with a habitualization of practice and becomes particularly exciting when institutionalized activities are passed on to people who were not involved from the outset, whereby the issue of legitimization is then added (Berger & Luckmann, 1966; Kervinen et al., 2020).

6. Discussion of the results

The results presented above are discussed in this chapter, including questions about support needed to promote outdoor education and where future studies on outdoor education at the secondary level should begin.

The results chapter showed a narrow literature base (in both English and German) about continuous, curriculum-oriented, subject-related

outdoor education at or including the secondary level. The main findings presented in this literature review are based on six articles. Therefore, the evidence and conclusions are based on a very small dataset. This is a limitation of the present literature review. Nevertheless, the six studies do provide some insight into outdoor education on continuous, curriculum-oriented, subject-related outdoor education at or including the secondary level. As the focus of the individual studies is different, relating the results to each other could at times be difficult. There is a clear need for more research on outdoor education at the secondary level.

Due to the small number and diversity of existing articles on secondary level outdoor education (compared to numerous articles on outdoor education at the primary level and the fact that less outdoor education takes place at the secondary level than at the primary level (Barfod et al., 2021; Scott et al., 2015; Williams & Scott, 2019; Winje & Løndal, 2021)), it is only possible to make assumptions about the reasons for the modest outdoor education practice at the secondary level, which will need to be empirically tested in the future. The analyzed articles show that the implementation of outdoor education is individual and teacher-dependent as well as mostly interdisciplinary. However, it is assumed that this is challenging at the secondary level for structural reasons (see also the reasons given by Williams & Scott, 2019, with the top three challenges for teachers being: time, evidence and management), especially as many subject teachers are involved who do not work together per se, and the timetable is correspondingly “fragmented” and offers very few opportunities for longer, continuous outdoor education units. According to one of the articles analyzed, the solution to this is for teachers to work together and go outside together (Duggan et al., 2021), which they do not always do (Svobodová et al., 2021). This shows the need for school improvement processes: The introduction of continuous, curriculum-based, subject-related outdoor education requires.

- orientation, for example by establishing a joint position regarding outdoor education and including outdoor education in the school program, connected to living a school culture that is conducive to outdoor education,
- exchange (e.g. meetings, visits) and development opportunities for teachers, and
- structural adjustments, for example to the timetable, possibly even to the subject table.

This means that the team of teachers and the school management, possibly even the school district, play an essential role in launching and implementing outdoor education, as can also be seen in the literature (Müller-Kuhn, 2024). It became clear in the literature review that outdoor education is more than just a change of location. This result confirms earlier findings according to which outdoor education has an influence on school order (Feichter, 2020; Sahrakhiz, 2018; Tyack & Tobin, 1994). This is associated with another desideratum that emerges from the literature review: There is a need for further training for teachers as well as appropriate consideration in the education of prospective teachers, so that teachers feel competent to teach the lesson content outdoors. This would potentially shift the focus of outdoor education, which currently tends to be on life skills (Becker et al., 2017; Mann et al., 2022), towards subject-specific skills (taught in an interdisciplinary way). This would bring outdoor education practice closer to Kühnis’ model (2024) and the question of where the “E” has gone in outdoor education (Pierce & Beames, 2024) would no longer need to be asked.

Regarding the subjects taught outdoors in the articles reviewed, it is striking that science is particularly emphasized. Other subjects – such as arts, math, and language, which are taught outdoors in primary schools – do not appear to be the main focus of outdoor education in secondary schools. Subject-specific skills can be taught in two ways: subject-separated, which at first glance would be conducive to high-stakes testing, or interdisciplinary, which would correspond to the real

world: 1) If outdoor education were more subject-oriented (whereby life skills often also form part of the curriculum), teachers would perhaps be less reluctant to use outdoor education, also in view of the high-stakes testing. Considering that research shows that outdoor education is effective (see overviews in e.g. Becker et al., 2017, Kuo et al., 2022; Mann et al., 2022) and that there is even a “dose-response relationship” (Kuo et al., 2022, p. 50), subject-oriented outdoor education would be a great benefit for students’ learning and, with high-stakes testing, ultimately also for the school’s reputation. In order to dispel the notions that students learn too little during outdoor education and outdoor education is not suitable for the subjects that are part of the high-stakes testing, additional research will be needed to provide even more evidence of the impact of outdoor education. 2) Outdoor education is often interdisciplinary and teaching refers to the real world, or this is formulated as a requirement in the analyzed articles. The interdisciplinarity and the reference to reality makes it difficult to recognize which subject content is currently being learned and which curriculum references are currently being made. Perhaps this is modern learning and preparation for the real world: no artificial division into subjects and no learning by means of representations, but rather interdisciplinary learning on the real object, as emphasized by Våljataga and Mettis (2022, p. 3): “Students learn by experiencing the real world in a natural, authentic setting, located at the source of data and natural phenomena by engaging in and through the local environment” (with reference to Glassman, 2001; Kilty & Burrows, 2020). The combination of the two perspectives – high-stakes testing and interdisciplinary learning on the real object – may seem challenging. The silver bullet will therefore be to find a way to teach interdisciplinarily outdoors and still deepen the subject content in such a way that teachers and students feel ready for high-stakes testing (if the future shows that these tests are to be continued). Given the advantages of real-world learning and the evidence that outdoor education improves learning outcomes (see overviews in e.g. Becker et al., 2017, Kuo et al., 2022; Mann et al., 2022), it is obvious that an interdisciplinary yet subject-specific approach to outdoor education makes sense to complement life skills learning outdoors. Nevertheless, further study that builds on the existing research is required to prove more generalizable evidence that the curriculum is also fulfilled in real world learning outdoors.

The literature review not only showed that outdoor education takes place in different ways, but that outdoor education is also embedded differently in the analyzed articles: Several articles referred to

Table 3

Overview of the desiderata for researchers and practitioners in order to promote outdoor education.

Desiderata for researchers: Need for more research ...	Desiderata for practitioners: Teachers/schools need ...	Desiderata for both: Researchers and practitioners need ...
... to provide generalizable evidence of effectiveness of outdoor education and prove compliance with the curriculum	... school improvement processes, especially providing: - Orientation - Exchange - Structural adjustments	... to shift the focus of outdoor education from life skills towards subject-specific skills ... (to provide) published examples of outdoor education at the secondary level
... on outdoor education at the secondary level in general	... training: Integration of outdoor education in the education of pre- and in-service teachers	
... which explains reasons for the modest outdoor education practice at the secondary level	... to find a way to teach interdisciplinarily outdoors and still deepen the subject content	
... about the embedding and impact of occasional outdoor education events		

environmental education and place-based education, as well as to the positive effects of outdoor education. However, there does not appear to be a uniform frame of reference or discourse to which the articles on outdoor education at the secondary level refer as standard in the articles analyzed.

Beyond the specific articles chosen for this literature review, further literature on outdoor education at the secondary level exists that focuses on different aspects. For instance, some literature describes outdoor education events that do not take place on a regular basis, for example, but rather one-time outdoor education events. Research is needed on how one-time or occasional outdoor education events are embedded into the indoor lessons and what significance and impact short outdoor experiences have.

All in all, additional published examples of outdoor education at the secondary level are needed – on the one hand as best practice examples for those schools that want to introduce outdoor education, and on the other hand in order to have broader evidence of outdoor education practice at the secondary level. Further research into outdoor learning at the secondary level and consideration of the findings from existing studies can help to ensure that outdoor education at the secondary level receives more attention in the future. [Table 3](#) provides an overview of the desiderata for researchers and practitioners in order to promote outdoor education.

7. Conclusion

For this systematic literature review on outdoor education at the secondary level, a systematic literature search was carried out in five databases, resulting in 150 different articles. The predefined selection criteria were applied to the research results in several steps. The procedure led to six articles dealing with continuous, curriculum-based, subject-related outdoor education. It became apparent that in the last five years, only a few articles have appeared on continuous, curriculum-based, subject-related outdoor education at the secondary level. Much more common were articles examining one-time outdoor education units, evaluations of specific lesson preparations with before and after measurements used to “prove” a learning gain for the students, but which could not be transferred to other situations, and articles discussing concrete environmental education, some of which took place in the classroom instead of outdoors.

In conclusion, it can be said that this literature review shows that there are indeed examples of outdoor education at the secondary level.

Appendix A. Search string

The complete search string is as follows (the spelling has been adapted to the respective search engine):

(TI outdoor education OR TI outdoor teaching OR TI outdoor school OR TI “outdoor learning” OR TI “nature based learning” OR TI “environmental education” OR TI “environmental learning” OR TI “nature school” OR TI “natural learning” OR TI “outdoor education” OR TI “outdoor education programs” OR TI “outdoor learning” OR TI “learning outdoor” OR TI “outdoor teaching” OR TI “teaching outdoor” OR TI “education outside the classroom” OR TI “out-of-classroom” OR TI “learning outside the classroom” OR TI “traditional school subjects taught in natural environments” OR TI “expeditionary learning” OR TI “adventure education” OR TI “adventure learning” OR TI “place-based education” OR TI “place-based learning” OR TI udeskole OR TI uteskole OR TI utomhuspedagogik OR TI friluftsliv OR TI “forest school” OR AB outdoor education OR AB outdoor teaching OR AB outdoor school OR AB “outdoor learning” OR AB “nature based learning” OR AB “environmental education” OR AB “environmental learning” OR AB “nature school” OR AB “natural learning” OR AB “outdoor education” OR AB “education outdoor” OR AB “outdoor education programs” OR AB “outdoor learning” OR AB “learning outdoor” OR AB “outdoor teaching” OR AB “teaching outdoor” OR AB “education outside the classroom” OR AB “out-of-classroom” OR AB “learning outside the classroom” OR AB “traditional school subjects taught in natural environments” OR AB “expeditionary learning” OR AB “adventure education” OR AB “adventure learning” OR AB “place-based education” OR AB “place-based learning” OR AB udeskole OR AB uteskole OR AB utomhuspedagogik OR AB friluftsliv OR AB “forest school”) AND (TI Sekundarschule OR TI Sekundarstufe OR TI “Zyklus 3” OR TI “secondary school” OR TI “secondary education” OR TI “lower secondary education” OR TI “mandatory secondary education” OR TI “middle school” OR TI “junior high school” OR TI “junior secondary” OR AB secondary school OR AB secondary level OR AB “cycle 3” OR AB “secondary school” OR AB “secondary education” OR AB “lower secondary education” OR AB “mandatory secondary education” OR AB “middle school” OR AB “junior high school” OR AB “junior secondary”)

However, these are isolated examples. Support through school improvement processes is not yet standard. Given structures such as subject teachers and short lesson durations as well as pressure due to high-stakes testing are at odds with the trend towards teaching outdoor education in an interdisciplinary way. The gap between outdoor education at the primary and secondary levels is considerable. If outdoor education is to be established at the secondary level, comprehensive school improvement processes are required: If a school decides on outdoor education, then outdoor education should be made the focus of the school as a whole.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used DeepL in order to improve language from an ESL perspective. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the contents as needed and sent it to an in-person editor for proofreading. The author takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that she has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix B. Article overview

Overview of included and excluded articles.

Article	Search engine(s)	Inclusion or exclusion
Ablak, S., & Yesiltas, E. (2020). Secondary school students' awareness of environmental education concepts. <i>Review of International Geographical Education Online</i> , 10 (3), 445–466.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Adeniyi, L. A., Oladehinde, G. J., Oladipupo, A. S., Adesoye, P. O., & Folorunso, S. A. (2024). Appraisal of solid waste generation in secondary schools towards sensitisation on environmental quality and education. <i>Management of Environmental Quality</i> , 35 (2), 299–313. https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-07-2023-0211	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Agirreazkuenaga, L., & Martinez, P. M. (2021). Secondary students' perception, positioning and insight on education for sustainability. <i>International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education</i> , 30 (3), 218–237. https://doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2021.1877952	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Altmeyer, S., & Dreesmann, D. (2020). The importance of religion for the evaluation of everyday ecological decisions by German adolescents. A case study with students in biology and religious education classes. <i>Worldviews: Global Religions, Culture, and Ecology</i> , 24 (3), 285–307. https://doi.org/10.1163/15685357-20203001	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Altmeyer, S., & Dreesmann, D. (2021). «The tree was there first» – using an everyday ecological dilemma to explore the personal orientations of secondary school students in environmental decision-making. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 27 (1), 67–87. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2020.1853062	GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Alves, G. V. B. C. L., Alitto, R. A., Antunes-Souza, T., & Martorano, S. A. A. (2024). Middle school students' perception of marine and coastal environments. <i>Journal of Biological Education</i> . https://doi.org/10.1080/00219266.2024.2320105	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Arbor, R. N., & Matteson, K. (2024). Interdisciplinary nature journaling improves mood and helps build connection in middle school students. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> . https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2024.2405901	WoS	Excluded in step 4 due to content
Arkan, K. (2023). A comparison of indoor and outdoor biology education: What is the effect on student knowledge, attitudes, and retention? <i>Journal of Biological Education</i> , 57 (4), 727–745. https://doi.org/10.1080/00219266.2021.1950809	ERIC, GreenFile, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Arslan, K., & Ari, A. G. (2024). Development of ecology achievement test for secondary school students. <i>Shanlax International Journal of Education</i> , 12, 166–179.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Arslan, K., & Karakus, N. (2024). Environmental teaching supported by web 2.0-based digital games for a sustainable life. <i>Sustainability</i> , 16 (22). https://doi.org/10.3390/su16229691	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Asfeldt, M., Purc-Stephenson, R., & Zimmerman, T. (2022). Outdoor education in Canadian post-secondary education: common philosophies, goals, and activities. <i>Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education</i> , 25 (3), 289–310. https://doi.org/10.1007/s42322-022-00102-4	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 4 due to content
Atabey, N. (2021). Exploring middle school students' environmental attitudes through ecocentrism and anthropocentrism. <i>International Online Journal of Education and Teaching</i> , 8 (3), 1580–1602.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ayerbe-Lopez, J., & Perales-Palacios, F. J. (2023). Evaluating a secondary education urban ecology project within the framework of a problem-based learning methodology. <i>Education Sciences</i> , 13 (9). https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13090915	PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Bartley-Carter, D. (2024). Placed-based teaching and learning: History lessons that liberate learning and build community outside of the classroom. <i>Perspectives on Urban Education</i> , 21 (1).	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Berker, A. (2024). Education and interest in environmental issues in Turkey: Evidence from a compulsory schooling law. <i>Applied Economics Letters</i> . https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2024.2332582	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Bhang, K. J., & Huh, J. R. (2023). Effectiveness of fine dust environmental education on students' awareness and attitudes in Korea and Australia using AR technology. <i>Sustainability</i> , 15 (22). https://doi.org/10.3390/su152216039	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Bopardikar, A., Bernstein, D., & McKenney, S. (2023). Boundary crossing in student-teacher-scientist-partnerships: Designer considerations and methods to integrate citizen science with school science. <i>Instructional Science</i> , 51 (5), 847–886. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-022-09615-3	ERIC, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Bopardikar, A., Bernstein, D., & McKenney, S. (2023). Designer considerations and processes in developing school-based citizen-science curricula for environmental education. <i>Journal of Biological Education</i> , 57 (3), 592–617. https://doi.org/10.1080/00219266.2021.1933134	ERIC, GreenFile, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Bowers, A. W., & Creamer, E. G. (2021). A grounded theory systematic review of environmental education for secondary students in the United States. <i>International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education</i> , 30 (3), 184–201. https://doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2020.1770446	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Bryce, C. J. C., Dadswell, K., Dallat, C., & Parker, A. G. (2024). Perceptions of empowerment and leadership in the context of outdoor education: a qualitative study in women participants. <i>Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education</i> , 27 (3), 413–436. https://doi.org/10.1007/s42322-023-00136-2	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Buldur, S., Bursal, M., Yalcin Erik, N., & Yucl, E. (2020). The impact of an outdoor education project on middle school students' perceptions and awareness of the renewable energy. <i>Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews</i> , 134. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110364	GreenFile, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Cabello Gomez, A., & Blanco Fontao, C. (2022). Sustainable development goals: Analysis of the knowledge and educative concerns in pre-service secondary education teachers from University of Leon. <i>Revista de Investigacion en Educacion</i> , 20 (2), 240–256. https://doi.org/10.35869/reined.v20i2.4228	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Canbazoglu Bilici, S., Kupeli, M. A., & Guzey, S. S. (2021). Inspired by nature: An engineering design-based biomimicry activity. <i>Science Activities-Projects and Curriculum Ideas in Stem Classrooms</i> , 58 (2), 77–88. https://doi.org/10.1080/00368121.2021.1918049	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Carvalho, S. C., Braga, H. O., de Santa-Maria, S., Fonte, B., Pereira, M. J., Garcia-Vinuesa, A., & Azeiteiro, U. M. (2021). An environmental education and communication project on migratory fishes and fishing communities. <i>Education Sciences</i> , 11 (7). https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11070337	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Celestino, T. (2023). High school sustainable and green chemistry: Historical-epistemological and pedagogical considerations. <i>Sustainable Chemistry</i> , 4 (3), 304–320. https://doi.org/10.3390/suschem4030022	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content

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Article	Search engine(s)	Inclusion or exclusion
Celik, C., & Aydin, G. (2024). Reflections of local learning environments on secondary school students: The wastewater treatment plant. <i>Journal of Science Learning</i> , 7 (1), 80–92.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Chappell, K., & Hetherington, L. (2024). Creative pedagogies in digital STEAM practices: Natural, technological and cultural entanglements for powerful learning and activism. <i>Cultural Studies Of Science Education</i> , 19 (1), 77–116. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11422-023-10200-4	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Chik, P. Y. Y., Leung, J. S. C., Bridges, S. M., Williams, G. A., Russell, B. D., & Not, C. A. (2024). Learning in and from the field: A qualitative study of affective engagement. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 30 (6), 900–925. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2023.2211752	ERIC, GreenFile, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Colagrande, E. A., & Farias, L. A. (2021). Presentation – Environmental Education and the Brazilian school context: current challenges, permanent reflections. <i>Educar em Revista</i> , 37. https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-4060.81232	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Cole, L. B., & Hamilton, E. M. (2020). Can a green school building teach? A pre- and post-occupancy evaluation of a teaching green school building. <i>Environment & Behavior</i> , 52 (10), 1047–1078. https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916518825283	GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Conrad, J. (2022). Desettling history: Non-indigenous teachers' practices and tensions engaging indigenous knowledges. <i>Teachers College Record</i> , 124 (1), 3–29. https://doi.org/10.1177/01614681221086069	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Coskuner, O. (2024). Use of a mobile plant identification application and the out-of-school learning method in biodiversity education. <i>Ecology And Evolution</i> , 14 (4). https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10957	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Costu, F., Demirci, E., & Costu, B. (2022). Investigation the effectiveness of storytelling on fifth grade turkish students' environmental problems. <i>Journal of Education in Science, Environment and Health</i> , 8 (3), 264–282.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
da Silva, W. C., Santos, F. B., Barbosa, A. V. C., Silva, L. K. X., da Silva, E. B. R., Costa, J. W. S., & Camargo Jr, R. N. C. (2024). Clinical and epidemiological aspects of patients injured by stingrays in the state of Pará, Brazil. <i>Acta Scientiarum-Health Sciences</i> , 46. https://doi.org/10.4025/actascihealthsci.v46i1.64579	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Del Rey, R., Ojeda, M., Mora-Merchán, J. A., Nieves Sánchez-Díaz, M., Morgado, B., & Lasaga, M. J. (2022). Environmental education: Effects on knowledge, attitudes and perceptions, and gender differences. <i>International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education</i> , 31 (4), 282–303. https://doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2021.1977004	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Deveci Topal, A., Dilek Eren, C., & Geçer, A. K. (2021). Chatbot application in a 5th grade science course. <i>Education and Information Technologies</i> , 26 (5), 6241–6265. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10627-8	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Dirr, K., & Meyer-Gutbrod, E. (2024). Using podcasts to bring national estuarine research reserves into the classroom. <i>Oceanography</i> , 37 (1), 154–159. https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2024.202	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Dos Santos, L. M. (2023). The relationship between environmental, outdoor and field education: A study in rural communities. <i>International Journal of Instruction</i> , 16 (1), 643–658.	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Down, M., Picknoll, D., Piggott, B., Hoyne, G., & Bulsara, C. (2023). "I love being in the outdoors": A qualitative descriptive study of outdoor adventure education program components for adolescent wellbeing. <i>Journal Of Adolescence</i> , 95 (6), 1232–1244. https://doi.org/10.1002/jad.12197	PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Drosos, D., Kyriakopoulos, G. L., Ntanos, S., & Parissi, A. (2021). School managers perceptions towards energy efficiency and renewable energy sources. <i>International Journal of Renewable Energy Development</i> , 10 (3), 573–584. https://doi.org/10.14710/ijred.2021.36704	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Duggan, G. L., Jarre, A., & Murray, G. (2021). Learning for change: Integrated teaching modules and situated learning for marine social-ecological systems change. <i>Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 52 (2), 118–132. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2020.1852524	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Included
Eggersen, D. (2024). Place-based reading: Literature didactics outside the classroom. <i>L1-Educational Studies in Language and Literature</i> , 24 (1), 1–19. https://doi.org/10.21248/l1esll.2024.24.1.384	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Esteban Ibanez, M., Musitu Ferrer, D., & Amador Munoz, L. V. (2022). School adjustment, empathy and connectedness with the natural environment in environmental education in Spanish secondary education. <i>Interdisciplinaria</i> , 39 (3), 243–262. https://doi.org/10.16888/interd.2022.39.3.14	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Frensley, B. T., Stern, M. J., & Powell, R. B. (2020). Does student enthusiasm equal learning? The mismatch between observed and self-reported student engagement and environmental literacy outcomes in a residential setting. <i>Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 51 (6), 449–461. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2020.1727404	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Frensley, B. T., Stern, M. J., Powell, R. B., & Sorice, M. G. (2022). Investigating the relationships among students basic psychological needs, engagement, and environmental literacy at a residential environmental education center. <i>Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 53 (4), 186–198. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2022.2081654	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Froberg, A., & Lundvall, S. (2022). Sustainable development perspectives in physical education teacher education course syllabi: An analysis of learning outcomes. <i>Sustainability</i> , 14 (10). https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105955	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Froberg, A., Wiklander, P., Baena-Morales, S., & Lundvall, S. (2023). How to teach about sustainable development in physical education? Examples from the perspectives of certified teachers in Sweden. <i>Frontiers in Education</i> , 8. https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1294763	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Gandolfi, H. E., Rushton, E. A. C., Luciano Fernandes Silva, & Maria Bernadete Sarti da Silva Carvalho. (2024). Teacher educators and environmental justice: Conversations about education for environmental justice between science and geography teacher educators based in England and Brazil. <i>Cultural Studies of Science Education</i> , 19 (2–3), 257–286. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11422-024-10212-8	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Garcia-Gonzalez, J. A., Garcia Palencia, S., & Sanchez Ondono, I. (2021). Characterization of environmental education in spanish geography textbooks. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13 (3). https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031159	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Gebeyehu, D., Dalelo, A., Fikadu Eshetu, Woldie Belachew, Wodaj, H., Abate, A., & Hagos, M. (2024). Energy-, environmental-, and climate change literacy among primary and middle school students. <i>International Journal of Research in Education and Science</i> , 10 (1), 100–124.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content

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Article	Search engine(s)	Inclusion or exclusion
Georgousis, E., Savelides, S., Mosios, S., Holokolos, M.-V., & Drinia, H. (2021). The need for geoethical awareness: The importance of geoenvironmental education in geoheritage understanding in the case of meteora geomorphes, Greece. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13 (12). https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126626	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Georgousis, E., Savelidi, M., Savelides, S., Holokolos, M.-V., & Drinia, H. (2021). Teaching geoheritage values: Implementation and thematic analysis evaluation of a synchronous online educational approach. <i>Heritage</i> , 4 (4), 3523–3542. https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage4040195	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Glackin, M., & King, H. (2020). Taking stock of environmental education policy in England – the what, the where and the why. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 26 (3), 305–323. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2019.1707513	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Gomez Galan, J., Figueroa Miranda, O., Lazaro Perez, C., & Angel Martinez-Lopez, J. (2021). Design proposal towards an interdisciplinary approach to environmental education: Theoretical analysis of an innovative practice. <i>International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation</i> , 16, 142–161. https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.5424	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Gruno, J., & Gibbons, S. L. (2021). Using discussion to inform action: Formative research on nature-based physical activity as a means of fostering relatedness for girls in physical and health education. <i>European Physical Education Review</i> , 27 (4), 743–760. https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336X21991181	ERIC, WoS	Included
Guo, F., Meadows, M. E., Duan, Y., & Gao, C. (2020). Geography pre-service teachers' perspectives on multimedia technology and environmental education. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12 (17). https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176903	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Hamilton, E., & Marckini-Polk, L. (2023). The impact of place-based education on middle school students' environmental literacy and stewardship. <i>Cogent Education</i> , 10 (1). https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2022.2163789	ERIC, WoS	Included
Hernandez, J., Skiba, J., German, M., Scherr, R., Huynh, T., Mathis, C., & Araya, M. (2022). Exploring sociopolitical landscapes in physics education. <i>Sustainability & Climate Change</i> , 15 (4), 279–288. https://doi.org/10.1089/scc.2022.0023	GreenFile	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Hooikaas, A. (2021). Stewarding places through geography in higher education. <i>Journal of Geography</i> , 120 (3), 108–116. https://doi.org/10.1080/00221341.2021.1895288	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Hoper, J. (2024). Mind the gap between chemistry and outdoor education: Primary and lower secondary preservice teachers' beliefs during an outdoor-based introduction to chemistry in science education. <i>Journal of Science Teacher Education</i> . https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2024.2406661	WoS	Included
Horst, R., James, K., Morales, E., & Takeda, Y. (2023). The intermingled meanings of phoneme: exploring transmodal, place-based poetry in an online social network. <i>Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy</i> , 66 (4), 249–256. https://doi.org/10.1002/jaal.1274	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ichsan, I. Z., Rahmayanti, H., Purwanto, A., Sigit, D. V., & Rahman, Md. M. (2020). PEB-COVID-19: Analysis of students behavior and ilmizi model in environmental learning. <i>Jurnal Iqra Kajian Ilmu Pendidikan</i> , 5 (1), 1–11. https://doi.org/10.25217/ji.v5i1.901	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ilham, Z., Zulkifli, N. E. I., Ismail, N. F., Danik, A. S., Abdul Halim-Lim, S., Wan-Mohtar, W. A. A. Q. I., & Jamaludin, A. A. (2022). Energy conservation: Awareness analysis among secondary school students. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 28 (6), 925–947. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2031902	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Imashev, G., Kuanbayeva, B. U., Yelezhanova, S. K., Myrzashova, A. N., Medeshova, A. B., Kochshanova, G., Zharylgapova, D. M., & Sultangaliyeva, L. S. (2020). Innovative approaches to the development of environmental education in high school. <i>Ad Alta-Journal of Interdisciplinary Research</i> , 10 (1, 10), 22–26.	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ingulfen, L., Furberg, A., & Knain, E. (2023). The role of teacher support in students' engagement with representational construction. <i>Cultural Studies of Science Education</i> , 18 (4), 1311–1341. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11422-023-10193-0	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Jane, J., Wattchow, B., & Thomas, G. (2022). "Immersed within the rock itself": Student experiences rock climbing in outdoor education. <i>Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education</i> , 25 (3), 341–361. https://doi.org/10.1007/s42322-022-00108-y	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Jurek, M., Frajer, J., Fiedor, D., Brhelová, J., Hercik, J., Jác, M., & Lehnert, M. (2022). Knowledge of global climate change among czech students and its influence on their beliefs in the efficacy of mitigation action. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 28 (8), 1126–1143. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2086687	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Kalayci Alas, D., & Koruturk, K. (2024). Exploring the impact of values education on sustainable environmental awareness and behavior among eighth-grade students. <i>Sustainability</i> , 16 (21). https://doi.org/10.3390/su16219302	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Kanada, M., Norman, P., Kaida, N., & Carver, S. (2023). Linking environmental knowledge, attitude, and behavior with place: A case study for strategic environmental education planning in Saint Lucia. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 29 (7), 929–950. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2074376	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Karim, N., Othman, H., Zaini, Z.-I. I., Rosli, Y., Wahab, M. I. A., Al Kanta, A. M., Omar, S., & Sahani, M. (2022). Climate change and environmental education: Stance from science teachers. <i>Sustainability</i> , 14 (24). https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416618	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Karpudewan, M. (2021). The influence of ethnicity and other socio-demographic characteristics on pro-environmental attitudes: a Malaysian perspective. <i>Local Environment</i> , 26 (10), 1284–1298. https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2021.1973976	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Kerr, K. (2020). Teacher development through coteaching outdoor science and environmental education across the elementary-middle school transition. <i>Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 51 (1), 29–43. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2019.1604482	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 4 due to structure
Kervinen, A., Uitto, A., & Juuti, K. (2020). How fieldwork-oriented biology teachers establish formal outdoor education practices. <i>Journal of Biological Education</i> , 54 (2), 115–128. https://doi.org/10.1080/00219266.2018.1546762	ERIC, GreenFile	Included
Khoa, L. V. (2022). Study on private upper secondary education in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. <i>Education Quarterly Reviews</i> , 5 (1), 70–80.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Kinch, R. A., Bobilya, A. J., Daniel, B., & Duncan, S. (2022). Indigenous storytelling, Cherokee traditional ecological knowledge, and place-based education. <i>Journal of Outdoor Recreation, Education, and Leadership</i> , 14 (4), 55–70.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content

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Article	Search engine(s)	Inclusion or exclusion
Kiraz, A., Antip, T. M., & Gunduz, S. (2020). Contributing water pollution control through the use of selected instructional strategies amongst secondary school students. <i>Desalination And Water Treatment</i> , 177, 257–263. https://doi.org/10.5004/dwt.2020.25011	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Koculu, A., & Topcu, M. S. (2024). Development and Implementation of a Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Unit: Exploration of Middle School Students' SDG Knowledge. <i>Sustainability</i> , 16 (2). https://doi.org/10.3390/su16020581	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Koulouri, P., Mogias, A., Mokos, M., Cheimonopoulou, M., Realdon, G., Boubonari, T., Previati, M., Formoso, A. T., Kideys, A. E., Hassaan, M. A., Patti, P., Korfiatis, K., Fabri, S., & Juan, X. (2022). Ocean literacy across the mediterranean sea basin: evaluating middle school students' knowledge, attitudes, and behavior towards ocean sciences issues. <i>Mediterranean Marine Science</i> , 23 (2), 289–301. https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.26797	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Kras, N. (2024). A model for embedding nature-based learning across disciplines: A pilot study at an urban community college. <i>Community College Enterprise</i> , 30 (1), 9–21.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Kulegel, S., & Topsakal, U. U. (2020). Secondary school students' perceptions about space camp: Space camp Turkey. <i>Journal of Education and Learning</i> , 9 (3), 154–162.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Lapena, J. (2023). Environmental education and the contributions of geography in its implementation at the Buenos Aires primary level of education. <i>Estudios Socioterritoriales</i> , 34. https://doi.org/10.37838/unicen/est.34-165	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Larrea, I., Muela, A., & Imaz, O. (2024). Student and teacher perceptions of the outdoor experience on traditional playgrounds: A case study. <i>Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning</i> , 24 (2), 302–316. https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2022.2160992	ERIC, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 4 due to content
Leitao, R., Maguire, M., Turner, S., & Guimaraes, L. (2022). A systematic evaluation of game elements effects on students' motivation. <i>Education and Information Technologies</i> , 27 (1, SI), 1081–1103. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10651-8	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Lindgren, S., Morris, K., & Price, A. (2021). Designing environmental storylines to achieve the complementary aims of environmental and science education through science and engineering practices. <i>Journal of Environmental Education</i> , 52 (4), 239–255. https://doi.org/10.1080/00958964.2021.1949569	ERIC, GreenFile, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Lombana, D. A. B., Ventura, R. B., Chen, Y. T., & Porfiri, M. (2023). Educating youth about human impact on freshwater ecosystems using an online serious game. <i>Ieee Transactions on Games</i> , 15 (4), 590–602. https://doi.org/10.1109/TG.2022.3185959	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Lovren, V. O., & Jablanovic, M. M. (2023). Bridging the gap: The affective dimension of learning outcomes in environmental primary and secondary education. <i>Sustainability</i> , 15 (8). https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086370	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Lynstad, I., & Saether, E. (2021). The concept of “friluftsliv literacy” in relation to physical literacy in physical education pedagogies. <i>Sport, Education and Society</i> , 26 (5), 514–526. https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2020.1762073	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Mahat, H., Norkhaidi, S. B., Saleh, Y., Hashim, M., Nayan, N., Said, Z. M., Matnoor, M., & Hamid, N. (2022). A study on the responsibility of environmental ethics among secondary school students in the 21st century. <i>International Journal of Educational Methodology</i> , 8 (3), 585–593.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Malik, H., Stronach, R. L., & Witzig, S. B. (2024). Nature photography: a spark for discussion and action on environmental issues. <i>Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education</i> . https://doi.org/10.1007/s42322-024-00187-z	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Marcum-Dietrich, N., Stunkard, C., Krauss, Z., Kerlin, S., Staudt, C., Muenz, T., & Kline, D. (2022). Stormy waters: COVID-19 transition to online learning for an environmental education middle school curriculum. <i>Science Educator</i> , 28 (2), 97–106.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Marques-Ibanez, A. M. (2023). Art education through the sustainable design of learning spaces. <i>International Journal of Education Through Art</i> , 19 (1), 113–133. https://doi.org/10.1386/eta_00122_1	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Martinez-Aznar, J., Calvo Sevillano, G., & Sanchez-Leon, N. (2022). Environmental literacy and ecosocial crisis: design and validation of a questionnaire for 4 ESO. <i>Revista de Investigacion en Educacion</i> , 20 (2), 257–273. https://doi.org/10.35869/reined.v20i2.4229	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Mónus, F. (2022). Environmental education policy of schools and socioeconomic background affect environmental attitudes and pro-environmental behavior of secondary school students. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 28 (2), 169–196. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2021.2023106	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Moser, A. de S., Torales Campos, M. A., & Meira Cartea, P. A. (2023). Environmental education in the context of climate emergency: adaptation and validation of the Resclima instrument for research in high school. <i>Remea-Revista Eletronica do Mestrado em Educacao Ambiental</i> , 40 (3), 300–317.	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Mujib, M., Mardiyah, M., & Suhermen, S. (2023). Development and psychometric properties of a questionnaire on environmental literacy in Indonesian secondary school. <i>Revista Fuentes</i> , 25 (3), 267–282. https://doi.org/10.12795/revistafuentes.2023.22642	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Mutlu, F., Nacaroglu, O., & Dogan, M. (2021). Awareness of the gifted students and their normally developing peers about environmental education concepts. <i>Acta Didactica Napocensia</i> , 14 (1), 2–16.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ndzimbomvu, N. T., Rampedi, I. T., & Kemp, M. E. (2021). Learning environmental issues from a secondary school curriculum: The case of learners in Mamelodi township, South Africa. <i>Sustainability</i> , 13 (16). https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169149	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Neo, X., & Schneider-Mayerson, M. (2022). Nature, disappeared: Anti-environmental values in Singapore's history textbooks, 1984–2015. <i>Environmental Education Research</i> , 28 (1), 56–74. https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2021.1968350	ERIC, GreenFile, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Neville, I. A., Petrass, L. A., & Ben, F. (2023). The impact of an outdoor learning experience on the development of english creative writing skills: An action research case study of year 7 and 8 secondary school students in Australia. <i>Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning</i> , 23 (2), 132–145. https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2021.1983445	ERIC, PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 4 due to content
Norman, T. A., & Wall, A. (2020). Curriculum integration: Walking the walk. <i>Current Issues in Middle Level Education</i> , 25 (1).	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content

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Article	Search engine(s)	Inclusion or exclusion
Nurke, M., Zhumabayeva, A., Adenova, L., Baikenova, S., & Abilkalamova, K. (2024). The visual arts' role in the development of students' noosphere worldview. <i>Journal of Education and E-Learning Research</i> , 11 (1), 8–16.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Nuwategeka, E., Mirembe, D. D., Milligan, L. O., & Aciro, T. (2024). Conflicted epistemologies in secondary school environmental education: implications for sustainable climate action in Uganda. <i>Compare – a Journal of Comparative and International Education</i> . https://doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2024.2378295	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ortiz, J. L., Conkey, A. A. T., Brennan, L. A., Fedynich, L. V., & Green, M. (2020). Wild bird workshop: A professional development opportunity for educators. <i>American Biology Teacher</i> , 82 (1), 3–10. https://doi.org/10.1525/abt.2020.82.1.3	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 4 due to content
Osunji, O. (2021). Relationship between consciousness about environmental education concepts in secondary school chemistry curriculum and attitude of students toward the environment in Kwara state. <i>Science Education International</i> , 32 (1), 80–84.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Özçelik, A., & Arik, S. (2022). Attitudes of secondary school students towards sustainable development. <i>International Online Journal of Education and Teaching</i> , 9 (4), 1987–2004.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Özer-Keskin, M., & Aksakal, E. (2020). An investigation of environmental literacy levels and environmental pollution images of 7th year pupils in primary education. <i>International Online Journal of Education and Teaching</i> , 7 (4), 1343–1368.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Ozkan, G., Turan, H., & Topsakal, U. U. (2020). Opinions of the sixth year students who participated in outdoor learning activity practices for science. <i>World Journal of Education</i> , 10 (2), 150–157.	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Palmos, D., Papavasileiou, C., Papakitsos, E. C., Vamvakeros, X., & Mavrakis, A. (2021). Enhancing the environmental programmes of secondary education by using web-tools concerning precaution measures in civil protection: The case of Western Attica (Greece). <i>Safety Science</i> , 135. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105117	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Pambudi, D. S. (2022). The effect of outdoor learning method on elementary students' motivation and achievement in geometry. <i>International Journal of Instruction</i> , 15 (1), 747–764. https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2022.15143a	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Parrish, A.-M., Okely, A. D., Salmon, J., Trost, S., Hammersley, M., & Murdoch, A. (2023). Making “being less sedentary feel normal” -Investigating ways to reduce adolescent sedentary behavior at school: A qualitative study. <i>The International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity</i> , 20 (1). https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-023-01444-y	PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Pereira, B. B., & Ha, S. (2024). Reconceptualized family resemblance approach to the nature of science in middle-school science textbooks from Brazil and South Korea regarding environmental issues. <i>Science & Education</i> . https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-024-00514-2	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Persich, G. D. O., Drehmer-Marques, K. C., & Tolentino-Neto, L. C. B. de. (2022). The potential of an investigative teaching sequence based on the analysis of secondary education curriculum policies. <i>Remea-Revista Eletronica Do Mestrado Em Educacao Ambiental</i> , 39 (2), 146–165.	WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to structure
Pirchio, S., Passiatore, Y., Panno, A., Cipparone, M., & Carrus, G. (2021). The effects of contact with nature during outdoor environmental education on students' wellbeing, connectedness to nature and pro-sociality. <i>Frontiers In Psychology</i> . https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.648458	PsychInfo, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
Polat, M. B., Karacizmeli, I. H., Atasoy, A. D., & Yesilnacar, M. I. (2024). Assessment of the knowledge, emotions and behaviours of secondary school students towards the environment and recycling in Southeastern Türkiye. <i>European Journal of Education</i> , 59 (3). https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12676	ERIC, WoS	Excluded in step 3 due to content
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Schrot, O. G., Traxler, J., Weifner, A., & Kretzer, M. M. (2021). Potential of “future workshop” method for educating adolescents about climate change mitigation and adaptation: A case from Freistadt, Upper Austria. <i>Applied Environmental Education and Communication</i> , 20 (3), 256–269. https://doi.org/10.1080/1533015X.2020.1816515	ERIC	Excluded in step 3 due to content
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